

A holistic security approach to protect Cloud-Native applications

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Abstract. The shift towards cloud-native applications has gained momentum in the past few years. Nevertheless, the inherent distributed architecture of these applications, in some cases across the edge and cloud continuum, represents unique security challenges. The more (micro-) components and network communications between them, the more complex detecting and mitigating security threats is. To tackle such issues, this paper presents a novel federated learning-based approach incorporating supervised machine learning approaches capable of performing traffic anomaly detection in such challenging environments, with a strong focus on three prominent challenges: which algorithm to use, which network features to consider and the data security and privacy. To evaluate the proposed approach, three supervised approaches commonly used for anomaly detection [26] were compared: Random Forest, SVMs and CNNs, in an isolated environment and then in a decentralised one, using four different performance metrics (i.e., accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score) and two types of attacks usually found in network environments: Denial of Service and Port Scan. In the validation scenario, the implemented approach with the best performance of f1-score presented 100.0% and 99.97%, respectively, for the Denial of Service and Port Scan attacks. The attained results allowed us to conclude the intrinsic value of the proposed approach for improving the security of emerging Cloud-Native applications and the value of the assessed algorithms for efficiently detecting network anomalies.

Keywords: cloud native; anomaly detection; supervised ML; federated learning;

1 Introduction

5G networks and Cloud-Native 5G environments require a different security approach when compared to traditional environments and applications, since these are no longer large monolithic architectures, but comprise numerous microservice-oriented components. Hence, 5G-enabled applications translate into a vast attack surface area (i.e., a more significant number of smaller, yet potentially exposed

parts) and increased network communications between components. Network traffic capture can no longer happen at a single point. Instead, decentralised and fine-grain network traffic inspection is needed at multiple infrastructure points. Detecting a network anomaly in such environments requires collecting and processing large amounts of network traffic. Hence, artificial intelligence (AI) driven approaches are becoming critical for supporting classifying and detecting anomalies, including cyber-attacks.

This publication explores the usage of AI algorithms as part of an AI-driven system for detecting network anomalies in cloud-native environments. Significant research exists about AI-driven network anomaly detection (AD). Still, there is no straightforward approach to cope with all the open challenges of such a research topic. This publication focuses on presenting a novel holistic security approach to protect cloud-native applications, with a strong focus on three challenges: the network features to consider for AD, the algorithm to use, and the data privacy. Bearing in mind the need for common ground to enable the comparison of the results, the feature vector of a well-known dataset, CIC-IDS2017 [5], has been adopted. As for the algorithms, three main classes of AI algorithms were reviewed and implemented: Decision Tree-based, Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The proposed solution has been designed in such a way that the collected data does not contain any personal information and it also never leaves the source component, thus increasing the data security and privacy, by minimizing the likelihood of potential data breaches. Then, the implemented methodology is presented and the essential building blocks of the proposed approach are overviewed: the network traffic collectors and the AI-driven detection component. Finally, the evaluation strategy is presented as well as the results of the three ML approaches in an isolated environment. Their evaluation was first conducted with a literature reference dataset (CIC-IDS2017) and later in a realistic distributed scenario where the trained models were placed in a federated environment, providing network traffic AD next to a PPDR micro-services oriented application.

This paper presents a novel FL-based approach enabling data privacy while leveraging the use of supervised ML approaches to perform binary traffic AD in cloud-native environments (with a strong strand on feature engineering), including its validation in a realistic environment.

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of network AD literature; Section 3 details the different steps taken on the design, testing and validation of the proposed approach; Section 4 presents the concluding remarks.

2 Related Work

This section presents a summary of the latest approaches referred to in the literature and used in the context of network AD as well as the latest Federated Learning (FL) approaches used for this purpose.

Ferrag et al. [1] present a hybrid classification system entitled Rules and Decision Tree-Based Intrusion Detection System (RDTIDS). Such a system corresponds to a hierarchical model built over two layers, considering two classifiers in the first level, where each one considers a different set of features and a third classifier on the second layer, that besides receiving the complete set of features as input, also receives the classification of the two first classifiers for each sample. The authors evaluate their approach using the CIC-IDS2017 [5] and the Bot-IoT [12], achieving the following results: 94.48% and 95.18% of Global Detection Rate (GDR), 96.67% and 97.00% of accuracy, and 1.14% and 1.12% of False Alarm Rate (FAR), respectively for the CIC-IDS2017 and Bot-IoT datasets. The authors concluded that the proposed system was able to provide the lowest FAR and highest detection rate for seven types of attacks.

Miao et al. [10] introduce two binary classification models based on SVMs, trained exclusively on normal samples. The authors evaluated their methods with synthetic datasets with UCI Machine Learning Repository datasets [22]. The authors considered the Area Under the Curve (AUC) as the evaluation metric, being the best and worst performances of 99.75% and 63.41% for the PenDigits and Abalone datasets, respectively, considering the doOCSVM approach. For the sparse doOCSVM approach, the best and worst approaches presented 95.28% and 64.52% for the PageBlocks and Abalone datasets, respectively.

Ullah et al. [23] present a CNN-based approach for AD. The authors took inspiration from a CNN approach initially used for image recognition and proposed three different configurations for their solution-oriented AD. The performance of the proposed approach is validated recurring to the BoT-IoT, IoT Network Intrusion, MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 and IoT-23 intrusion detection datasets. The authors stated that the proposed approach achieves higher performance than existing classification strategies, being the lowest *accuracy* achieved of 99.03% for all four datasets.

Yi et al. [8] present a communication-efficient on-device FL approach for detecting anomalies named Attention Mechanism-Based Convolutional Neural Network-Long Short-Term Memory (AMCNN-LSTM), characterising it as a Deep Anomaly Detection (DAD) approach, which leverages the use of a CNN to capture the fine-grained features of time-series data and uses the LSTM module to detect the anomalies. To improve the traditional overhead associated with FL communications between the edge devices and the aggregator, the authors suggest a Top-k selection-based gradient compression scheme which aims at reducing the exchanged parameters between both parties. The authors compared the performance of their approach with CNN-LSTM, LSTM, Gate Recurrent Units (GRUs), Stacked Auto-encoders (SAEs) and SVM using the following datasets: power demand, space shuttle, ECG and engine. The results graphically presented show that the proposed approach achieves the highest accuracy on all four datasets compared to other competing methods. The authors claim that the model presents better robustness to different datasets due to the on-device FL framework used to train and update the model, which makes it easier to learn the time-series features from different edge devices. The proposed gradi-

ent compression mechanism based on Top-k selection improves the framework’s communication efficiency and reduces 50% of the execution time of the FL training process.

Virraji et al. [11] propose a FL approach for time-series anomaly detection, utilizing GRUs and an ensemble composed of Random Forest (RF) models. These models perform parallel classification, and their collective decision is weighted. The authors compared GRUs and LSTMs and found that GRUs outperformed LSTMs in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency. The FL approach was further evaluated against a centralized version in a virtual scenario with multiple edge devices and a central aggregator, using the Modbus-based network dataset. Results indicate that FL achieves higher accuracy in fewer epochs, sometimes taking only 50% of the training time compared to the centralized approach. On average, the FL approach achieved 90.26% accuracy, while the non-FL approach reached 86.13%.

The reviewed approaches focus on AD, applying (at least) one of the implemented algorithms or evaluating their approaches with the CIC-IDS2017 dataset. Despite its promising results, [1] fails to address the issue of data privacy and security, and also the replication of this system into a distributed environment seems unlikely due to its complexity and computational demands. The AD approach proposed at [10], does not require anomalous data to be trained, which may present as an advantage in a future application to a federated environment. Nonetheless, the obtained results and the lack of focus on the way the data is handled, stand as some aspects for improvement. The compression mechanism for the communications linked to the behaviour of FL, introduced at [8], stand as a positive aspect, yet a proper validation using the CIC-IDS2017 dataset both on centralised and distributed environments could support its effectiveness for AD. The approach presented at [11] fails short on being validated at a non-emulated scenario and with other datasets beyond the Modbus dataset.

Addressing some of the aspects previously mentioned, our approach explores the application of traditional supervised approaches (Random Forest [24], SVMs [4] and CNN [23]) for network AD in cloud native environments. To strengthen the feasibility of our approach, we validate it in a realistic scenario with data from a micro-services oriented application, which presents a step further when compared to the existing literature.

3 Holistic Security Approach

3.1 Architecture

The proposed approach focus on the security of cloud-native applications by performing traffic anomaly classification over all the inbound and outbound network traffic, therefore following a holistic approach. The architecture considers the major characteristics of a FL-based approach, including the ability to train AI models on decentralised data, thus avoiding potential data breaches that could compromise data security and privacy. Figure 1 presents the architecture

of the proposed solution, where it is possible to find five major components: (i) Collector; (ii) Agent; (iii) Dashboard; (iv) Report Interface; and (v) Aggregator. Beyond the normal traffic generated by standard application service users, this architecture also considers internal and external attackers.

Fig. 1. Proposed Approach

The Collector is responsible for collecting the network inbound and outbound traffic passing through the main network interface. This information is then coupled into flows and stored until it is classified. Then, the Agent, where the ML models reside, is responsible for inferencing the stored data, and identifying the potential malicious flows. These are later reported to the Dashboard and to the Report Interface. The Dashboard consists of a GUI that provides observability over the inbound and outbound traffic of the protected network application, whilst the Report Interface enables the report of KPIs, namely via MQTT. The Aggregator corresponds to the brain of the federated environment, being responsible for handling the Agent’s training process and aggregating and distributing the updated ML models.

The architecture has been designed to minimise any potential data breaches, thus tackling the issue of data privacy and security. The data is never shared with any component outside of the Agent component, never leaving the origin component (i.e., Kubernetes POD), where it is exclusively utilized for inference and local training. After each training round, the updated weights matrix of the model present on each Agent is shared with the Aggregator, which, in turn, combines the individual weights and creates an updated global model. This way, it is possible to leverage the knowledge of different federated instances while only keeping a diminished set of information about these models (e.g., weights between layers), thus reducing the space needed to store the AI models as well as the computational requirements to train a model, since this effort is distributed among the different Agents.

3.2 Building the Approach

Figure 2 illustrates the training and evolution methodology followed while building the proposed approach.

Fig. 2. Training and Evaluation methodology overview

The first step consisted on pre-processing the CIC-IDS2017 dataset, followed by its division in a way to leave a hold-out section, later used for validation purposes. Also, the validation strategy used a *k-fold* cross-validation method. The training set was balanced using a SMOTE approach for each *k-fold* (i.e., training and testing sets). Then, the algorithm was trained and evaluated in the training and test sections. The value used for K was 5, acknowledging that 5 or 10 are values referred to as reference values in the literature ([9], [6]). For each iteration, new algorithm instances were trained with the corresponding training set and later evaluated with the test sets. The metrics used to decide the best instance were: accuracy, f1-score, precision and recall. Upon finding the best instance, the algorithm performance and validation were tested with the remaining Hold-Out section of the dataset using the same set of metrics previously mentioned. The process was repeated for each evaluated algorithm: Random Forest, SVM and CNN.

Pre-processing the dataset When pre-processing the CIC-IDS2017 dataset, the first step was to remove a set of different features deemed as non-relevant to the training process (i.e., label, source and destination IPs). Additionally, *timestamp* was also discarded, since the malicious attacks (per dataset) all contained relatively close values, corresponding to the intervals when the datasets were collected.

Moreover, a correlation between the timestamp and the label of each sample present on the training sets is undesired, since its value should not be linked with the respective sample label (i.e., normal or malicious). The next step was to analyse the data integrity. A small percentage of missing values, around 1%,

was found and removed. Considering such a reduced percentage, the impact of removing such samples is expected not to be quite significant. Considering the high range of values for the different features, we applied the min-max normalisation [16] technique.

Balancing the dataset To balance the dataset, two major *oversampling* strategies were implemented: random oversampling [17] and Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) [20]. The random oversampling approach randomly duplicates samples of the minority class and adds them to the training dataset, while SMOTE synthesises new examples from the existing samples. The most considerable advantage of the latter is the introduction of new information in the dataset.

Finding the most discriminant features Acknowledging the impact that a high number of features may present on the classification performance of an algorithm, and also aiming to reduce the complexity of the data being handled, we conducted an additional evaluation to find the most discriminant features using the Kruskal-Wallis test [25].

Fig. 3. Kruskal-Wallis test results for the *DoS* attack (CIC-IDS2017 dataset)

Figure 3 presents the 30 more discriminant features for the *DoS* attack, present in the CIC-IDS2017 dataset, according to the performed Kruskal-Wallis test. This test was conducted with a different number of features, being the scenario with 30 features the one where all the considered algorithms yielded better results. The values attained with this test enabled the comparison of

classification performances for each of the implemented algorithms, considering the same set of features for each attack.

3.3 Data collection

Figure 4 illustrates the network flows and metrics collection strategy.

Fig. 4. Network flow and metrics collection

There is no consensus in the literature about the complete list of features to use either on per-packet or per-flow approaches, which ultimately affect the performance of the AI algorithms. Moreover, such differences make it challenging to compare different approaches. We use the same feature vector (i.e., the list of features extracted from each flow) as present in the CIC-IDS2017 dataset [5]. Such a feature vector is one of the most comprehensive flow-based list of features. Their adoption allowed us to have a consistent baseline to compare later the achieved values with a state-of-the-art baseline using the CIC-IDS2017 dataset.

The packets were retrieved and aggregated using NFStream [14]. Hence, the original flows were further processed to form a dataset with the same feature vector as the CIC-IDS2017. Afterwards, the feature vectors are sent to the detection module, where pre-processing dataset techniques (detailed in Section 3.2), are applied. Later, the resulting feature vector is handed over to a binary ML-based classifier, classifying the flow as normal or malicious.

3.4 Implemented Approaches

Three supervised machine learning approaches were selected to be implemented: Random Forest, SVM and CNN. Their choice arises from a previous analysis of the existent SoA on network AD, where we verified that the most promising approaches were using these models. Random Forest was implemented using `sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier` [18] class. The performance of this algorithm was quite good throughout the different tests, with the algorithm presenting performance metric values always above 99%.

SVM was implemented using `sklearn.svm.SVC` class [19]. Acknowledging the importance of the C and γ input parameters for the kernel functions, a search grid approach was applied to identify the best combination of parameters, being $1.00e + 03$ and $1.00e - 05$ the chosen values, respectively for C and γ .

The CNN approach was implemented using a sequential model [21], with the following list of layers: 1D convolution layer, Dense layer, Flatten layer and a MaxPooling1D layer [7].

Table 1 presents the best set of results attained by the three implemented approaches for the CIC-IDS2017 dataset during the implementation stage. Overall, the three algorithms presented good performances when classifying the mentioned dataset. Random Forest achieved the best performance metrics, followed by the SVM and CNN with slightly lower values. Despite this, and bearing in mind the lowest *f1-score* achieved (i.e., 99.80%), all the approaches presented good performances.

Table 1. Algorithms performance with CIC-IDS2017 dataset

Algorithm	Attack	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
RF	DoS	100.00%	99.99%	99.99%	99.99%
	PS	100.00%	99.98%	99.99%	99.99%
SVM	DoS	99.94%	99.92%	99.92%	99.92%
	PS	99.70%	99.91%	99.80%	99.82%
CNN	DoS	99.94%	99.87%	99.88%	99.90%
	PS	100.00%	99.93%	99.95%	99.96%

3.5 Validation methodology

Beyond developing and testing the proposed approach, we have also sought to validate its correct behaviour in a realistic scenario. Such a process is described throughout this section.

Figure 5 illustrates the overall validation scenario. Three Kubernetes clusters were used, and the Mobitrust [3] (a PPDR micro-services oriented cloud-native application) deployment was replicated in each. The Collector and the Agent components were deployed next to the Mobitrust components and were connected to a single *Aggregator*, deployed in a separated *namespace* in one of the clusters.

The best-trained instances of the implemented approaches were used to perform the network traffic classification. The evaluation process was repeated three times, each one using a different algorithm (i.e., Random Forest, SVM and CNN), where the following steps were sequentially repeated: (i) deployment of Mobitrust application in a Kubernetes environment (with five simulated devices); (ii) continuous traffic collection during four hours; (iii) first federated training round (after four hours); (iv) execution of the attacks; (v) performance evaluation.

The round of attacks was conducted using a bash script, where the *mqtt-stresser* [13] and *nmap* [15] tools were used to perform the *DOS* attack and the *Port Scan* attack, respectively. In this specific scenario, an external virtual machine (VM) has been used to originate the attacks.

Fig. 5. Validation Scenario

3.6 Results and Discussion

This section presents the performance of each of the three implemented approaches (i.e., *Random Forest*, *SVM* and *CNN*) during the validation phase where a realistic scenario was replicated.

Table 2 presents the performance achieved by each of the three implemented approaches. It is possible to notice a slight overall decrease for the three algorithms compared to the scenario with the reference dataset, where all the algorithms presented performance metric values equal to or above 99.80%. Nevertheless, the three implemented approaches presented overall good performance, with the worst registered performance associated with the SVM approach for the *PS* attack with the value of the *f1-score* metric of 90.58%.

Table 2. Algorithms performance in a realistic scenario

Algorithm	Attack	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
RF	DoS	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	PS	99.93%	100.00%	99.96%	99.99%
SVM	DoS	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	PS	99.79%	98.32%	90.58%	98.43%
CNN	DoS	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	PS	98.37%	99.72%	97.47%	99.62%

Random Forest was the algorithm that presented better and more consistent results throughout the different experiments, presenting the highest values for the considered performance metrics in most tests. On one hand, the *SVM* presented excellent performance metric values (in some cases, the best values) for a sub-set of datasets coming from the CIC-IDS2017, where its worst performance produced a *f1-score* of 0.97. On the other hand, during the experiments

conducted with the set of collected datasets, the performance of the SVM-based approach did not deliver consistent good performances, achieving the worst classification in the *DoS* scenarios with a *f1-score* of 0.19. As for the *PS* samples, the attained performances were more consistent, with the algorithm achieving good results.

The overall quality of the performances achieved by the *CNN* was similar to the one attained by *Random Forest*. Despite this, it is worth highlighting that the lowest values of *f1-score* for both the algorithms happened for the *PS* attack of the collected dataset, which might suggest some peculiar dataset characteristic that results in this slight decrease of performance. Despite this, identifying such details was not pursued in the scope of this work.

The proposed solution considered two attacks, both during the training and validation phases, however, the process may be quickly replicated for other attacks. Moreover, the detection module of the proposed approach may also evolve into an ensemble approach, where multiple algorithms trained to detect different attacks would reside and classify the network traffic, thus evolving to a multi-classification system, safeguarding the capability of recognising attacks individually.

The success of any ML based approach is intrinsically linked with the choice and tuning of the used ML models. To this end, the ability of periodically training such models helps to keep them up to date, which is particularly beneficial if the network conditions frequently change. The periodicity of such training rounds may be considered an optimisation problem, in the sense that frequent training rounds may result in updated models, but at the cost of heavier computational costs. In addition, the typical difference of computational capabilities into a distributed environment (namely, with core and edge devices), may be another variable to consider when deciding on the frequency of the training rounds. Naturally, considering the four hours training period, the computational costs inherent to such operation are considerably reduced, when compared to lowest ones. Despite this, the use of supervised approaches presents the drawback of requiring a dataset of malicious data to be used to train, in conjunction with the normal one collected from the underlying application. Such drawback may not be relevant in centralised scenarios (for instance) where the computational resources are usually not a motive of precaution, yet, in edge devices this may pose as an imperative obstacle. The use of unsupervised approaches may present a clear advantage in this situations, since these do not require any data beyond the one already being collected. However, unsupervised approaches usually present lower classification performances, which may compromise the ability of the solution to effectively detect network anomalies.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents a FL-based framework for AD in the context of a cloud-native application and cloud-native 5G environments. The security of applications being executed in these new paradigms supported by ML approaches is

increasingly relevant, as discussed during this work. The main contribution of this work corresponds to a novel FL based approach that leverages the use of supervised ML approaches for traffic AD in cloud-native environments, focused on three main challenges: which algorithm to use, which network features to consider and data security and privacy concerns. It has been decided to adopt the features vector defined in the CIC-IDS2017 dataset and to understand which features were deemed relevant for the classification process, which was achieved using the Kruskal-Wallis test. To perform the traffic classification, we have selected three supervised approaches (Random Forest, SVM and CNN). The adoption of a federated-based approach enables us to tackle the issue of data privacy since the ML models are trained locally, thus avoiding sending all the collected data to a centralised location to perform the training rounds.

For future work, it could be interesting to expand the set of algorithms being used and the set of attacks being considered. Exploring the addition of Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) [2] into the existing architecture is also a step for future work as a way to deepen the data privacy on FL environments, beyond further validation with other cloud-native applications.

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References

1. FERRAG, M. A., MAGLARAS, L., AHMIM, A., DERDOUR, M., AND JANICKE, H. Rdtids: Rules and decision tree-based intrusion detection system for internet-of-things networks. *Future Internet* 12, 3 (2020).
2. GU, X., SABRINA, F., FAN, Z., AND SOHAIL, S. A review of privacy enhancement methods for federated learning in healthcare systems. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20, 15 (2023).
3. HENRIQUES, J., GOMES, A., AND CORDEIRO, L. Iot for improving first responders' situational awareness and safety on federated 5g testbeds.
4. HOSSEINZADEH, M., RAHMANI, A., VO, B., BIDAHI, M., MASDARI, M., AND ZAN-GAKANI, M. Improving security using svm-based anomaly detection: issues and challenges. *Soft Computing* 25 (02 2021), 1–29.
5. Intrusion detection evaluation dataset (cic-ids2017). <https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ids-2017.html>. Accessed: 2022-08-25.
6. JAMES, G. *An Introduction to Statistical Learning*. 2013.
7. Keras: Deep learning for humans. <https://keras.io>. Last access: 2023-08-01.
8. LIU, Y., GARG, S., NIE, J., ZHANG, Y., XIONG, Z., KANG, J., AND HOS-SAIN, M. S. Deep anomaly detection for time-series data in industrial iot: A

- communication-efficient on-device federated learning approach. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 8 (2020), 6348–6358.
9. MAX KUHN, K. J. *Applied Predictive Modeling*. 2013.
 10. MIAO, X., LIU, Y., ZHAO, H., AND LI, C. Distributed online one-class support vector machine for anomaly detection over networks. *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics* 49, 4 (2019), 1475–1488.
 11. MOTHUKURI, V., KHARE, P., PARIZI, R. M., POURIYEH, S., DEGHANTANHA, A., AND SRIVASTAVA, G. Federated-learning-based anomaly detection for iot security attacks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 9, 4 (2022), 2545–2554.
 12. MOUSTAFA, N. The bot-iot dataset. <https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/r7v2-x988>. Accessed: 2022-08-25.
 13. Mqtt stresser. <https://github.com/inovex/mqtt-stresser>. Last access: 2022-08-25.
 14. Nfstream: Flexible network data analysis framework. <https://www.nfstream.org/>. Last access: 2022-08-25.
 15. Nmap. <https://github.com/nmap/nmap>. Last access: 2022-08-25.
 16. OBAID, H. S., DHEYAB, S. A., AND SABRY, S. S. The impact of data pre-processing techniques and dimensionality reduction on the accuracy of machine learning. In *2019 9th Annual Information Technology, Electromechanical Engineering and Microelectronics Conference (IEMECON)* (2019), pp. 279–283.
 17. Randomoversampler. https://imbalanced-learn.org/dev/references/generated/imblearn.over_sampling.RandomOverSampler.html. Last access: 2022-08-25.
 18. sklearn.ensemble.randomforestclassifier. <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier.html>. Last access: 2023-08-01.
 19. sklearn.svm.svc. <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.svm.SVC.html>. Last access: 2023-08-01.
 20. Smote. http://glemaitre.github.io/imbalanced-learn/generated/imblearn.over_sampling.SMOTE.html. Last access: 2022-08-25.
 21. The sequential class. <https://keras.io/api/models/sequential/>. Last access: 2023-08-01.
 22. Uci machine learning repository. <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/index.php>. Last access: 2022-08-25.
 23. ULLAH, I., AND MAHMOUD, Q. H. Design and development of a deep learning-based model for anomaly detection in iot networks. *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), 103906–103926.
 24. VUONG, T. P., LOUKAS, G., GAN, D., AND BEZEMSKIJ, A. Decision tree-based detection of denial of service and command injection attacks on robotic vehicles. In *2015 IEEE International Workshop on Information Forensics and Security (WIFS)* (2015), pp. 1–6.
 25. XIA, Y. Chapter eleven - correlation and association analyses in microbiome study integrating multiomics in health and disease. In *The Microbiome in Health and Disease*, J. Sun, Ed., vol. 171 of *Progress in Molecular Biology and Translational Science*. Academic Press, 2020, pp. 309–491.
 26. ZHU, M., YE, K., AND XU, C.-Z. Network anomaly detection and identification based on deep learning methods. In *Cloud Computing – CLOUD 2018* (Cham, 2018), M. Luo and L.-J. Zhang, Eds., Springer International Publishing, pp. 219–234.